

Triaryltin and Diarylthallium Cyanides

T. N. SRIVASTAVA, S. N. BHATTACHARYA & K. K. BAJPAI

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow

Received 2 February 1971

Several triaryltin and diarylthallium cyanides (aryl = phenyl, *o*-m and -*p*-tolyl) have been prepared and characterised. Their structures on the basis of i.r. data are discussed and are found to be in favour of carbon-bonded molecules.

In continuation to our studies on organometallic pseudohalides of group-III and IV elements¹⁻¹⁰, we now report the syntheses and characterisation of some triaryltin and diarylthallium cyanides.

While the structural isomerism associated with a cyanide group *viz.*, the presence of the $-C \equiv N$ cyanide or $-N \equiv C$ isocyanide in alkyltin (iso)-cyanides have long been controversial¹¹⁻¹³ that of alkylthallium cyanides¹⁴ are well established. The preparation of the phenyl derivatives of tin^{15,16} and thallium¹⁷ by various methods appear to be the only aspect studied without much implication as to the nature of attachment of the CN group to the arylmetallic moieties. The method employed in the present work for the synthesis of triaryltin compounds by the reaction of silver cyanide with the corresponding triaryltin iodide is comparatively convenient specially since unlike the trialkyltin (iso)cyanides^{11-13,18} attempts to prepare the triphenyltin compound from the hydroxide and aqueous hydrocyanic acid or from triphenyltin chloride and potassium cyanide failed¹⁵. The alternative routes^{15,16} involve the use of hazardous anhydrous hydrogen cyanide as reactant or reaction medium. By choosing a suitable combination of solvents the diarylthallium cyanides have now been obtained and the melting point of diphenylthallium cyanide erroneously reported¹⁷ earlier is now corrected.

EXPERIMENTAL

Triaryltin iodides were prepared by the iodination of the corresponding tetraaryltin as reported earlier^{1,4,5}. Diarylthallium chloride were obtained from the reaction of tetrahydrated thallium (III) chloride with diaryltin dichloride followed by extraction with pyridine¹⁹.

Triaryltin cyanides: To 5 g. of dry silver cyanide suspended in 25 ml. of chloroform was slowly added 3 g. of the triaryltin iodide in 15 ml. of chloroform. The mixture was refluxed for 15 mins. and then filtered hot. The solvent was removed by distillation from the filtrate and the residual solid was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether.

Diarylthallium cyanides : The reaction between diarylthallium chloride and potassium cyanide in a mixture of pyridine water (1 : 1) solvent precipitated the required compound. Thus, a solution of 5 g. of diarylthallium chloride in 80 ml. of pyridine water mixture was treated with an excess of saturated aqueous solution of potassium cyanide and stirred for about 3 hrs at 70°. The precipitated light yellow diarylthallium cyanide was filtered, washed with water, alcohol and finally with ether and dried at 90°.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental results are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Experimental Results for Triaryltin and Diarylthallium cyanides

Compounds	m.p.	C%	H%	N%
(<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃) ₃ SnCN	120°	62.7	4.6	3.1
(<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃) ₃ SnCN	80°	62.3	4.5	3.3
(<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃) ₃ SnCN	195°	62.5	4.6	3.1
Calcd. for C ₂₂ H ₂₁ NSn	...	63.3	5.0	3.3
(<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃) ₂ TlCN	258°d	43.2	3.4	3.6
(<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃) ₂ TlCN	264°d	44.0	3.6	3.2
(<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃) ₂ TlCN	196°d	43.2	3.4	3.3
Calcd. for C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N'Tl	...	43.6	3.3	3.3
(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ TlCN	274°d*	40.5	2.8	3.7
Calcd. for C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N'Tl	...	40.6	2.6	3.6

* Reported 318°d by Challenger and Richards¹⁷.

d = decomposition.

The tritolyltin cyanides are white, well defined, sharp melting crystalline solids and like the triphenyltin^{15,16} compound undergo hydrolysis on contact with water, to yield the corresponding hydroxide, liberating hydrogen cyanide.

Presumably the ease of hydrolysis prevent the isolation of the triaryltin compounds from aqueous medium a method very commonly employed for the corresponding alkyl analogues^{11,13,18}.

The diarylthallium cyanides are not very different from the dimethyl compound¹⁴, thus all decompose at their melting points and are not easily hydrolysed by moisture. However, the aryl compounds, unlike the alkyls are only sparingly soluble in water and solvents like benzene and ether. The aryl compounds are soluble in pyridine and dimethylformamide probably through the formation of molecular addition compounds, from which the original, compounds can be recovered on distilling off the solvents. Like the dimethyl compound which behaves as a strong electrolyte [Me₂Tl]⁺CN⁻ in water the diaryl compounds were found to be ionized in dimethyl formamide.

Infra red spectra : The infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded in the range 4000–700 cm^{-1} . The absorption associated with the stretching of the cyanide group is listed in Table 2 and for purposes of comparison the corresponding absorption of trialkyltin and dialkylthallium cyanides are also included.

TABLE 2

Absorption for the Cyanide Group in $R_3\text{SnCN}$ and $R_2\text{TlCN}$

R =	$R_3\text{SnCN}$		$R_2\text{TlCN}$	
	Frequency (cm^{-1})	Ref.	Frequency (cm^{-1})	Ref.
C_6H_5	2169	This work	2100	This work
<i>o</i> - $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3$	2170	This work	2107	This work
<i>m</i> - $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3$	2172	This work	2105	This work
<i>p</i> - $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3$	2174	This work	2108	This work
Alkyl	2169 ± 6	(10, 12, 15)	2101	(13)

The frequency listed for the trialkyltin compounds $2169 \pm 6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are those observed for several alkyl^{11,13,16} compounds. Unlike the alkylsilicon¹¹ and alkylgermanium¹¹ (iso) cyanides the organotin compounds give only a single infra-red $\text{C} \equiv \text{N}$ band. The organic isonitriles $\text{R}-\text{NC}$ absorb at a lower frequency 2160–2120 cm^{-1} than the nitriles $\text{R}-\text{CN}$, 2260–2220 cm^{-1} ,^{20,21}. Attributing the higher frequency band to the $\text{C} \equiv \text{N}$ stretch and the lower frequency band to the $-\text{N} \equiv \text{C}$ stretch an equilibrium mixture of both forms have been proposed for silicon and germanium compounds¹¹. Ebsworth²² points out that the molecules which give two absorptions the weak lower frequency absorption might be due to overtone or combination modes while microwave²³, proton NMR²³, and X-ray²⁴ studies of similar compounds provide convincing evidences in favour of normal cyanide structures.

As in the asymmetric stretching vibration of the azides²⁵, isocyanates⁴ and fulminates²⁶ of the group-IV arylmetallic compounds it is interesting to note that the $\text{C} \equiv \text{N}$ stretching vibration gradually shifts to lower frequency from organic nitriles 2260–2220 cm^{-1} (^{20,21}) to triarylsilicon 2188 cm^{-1} (²⁷) to triarylgermanium 2180–2176 cm^{-1} ² to triaryltin 2174–2163 cm^{-1} (Table 2) to aryllead 2158 cm^{-1} ,²⁸ cyanides with the increase in the atomic number of the central metal atom, an order quite often arrived at by other spectroscopic methods²⁹. The $\text{N} \equiv \text{C}$ stretching of organic isonitriles which appear at $2140 \pm 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ would be expected to have a still lower frequency in order to be associated and attached to aryltin moieties and could not appear at such high frequencies observed in the present work. Hence the triaryltin cyanides have a carbon-bonded structure.

Experimental evidence in support of nitrogen-bonded iso structures, for instance, the reaction with sulphur^{11,13} has lately been questioned and explained as a possible rearrangement of the normal cyanide with the formation of the transient intermediate isocyanide³⁰, followed by the reaction with sulphur

or, the reaction could take place by formation of the thiofulminate (CNS), followed by rearrangement

in either case, the reaction implies lability of Sn-C bond in the normal cyanide. Further chemical evidence in support of normal form is the behaviour as a weak base towards phenol²³.

Coates and Mukherjee¹⁴ observed the C \equiv N stretch as a single band at 2101 cm⁻¹ in dimethylthallium cyanide as compared to the absorptions at 2200 \pm 25 cm⁻¹ for the corresponding analogues of other group-III metals. Since the terminal cyanide groups appear at a lower frequency than those of bridging cyanide (-C \equiv N \rightarrow) tetrameric bridged structures were proposed for cyanides other than that of dimethyl thallium. The diarylthallium cyanides have the C \equiv N stretch at 2108-2100 (Table 2) almost same as for the dimethyl compound and very close to the C \equiv N absorption for sodium 2085 cm⁻¹ and potassium 2076 cm⁻¹. This along with the fact that diaryl compounds are ionised in DMF strongly support their ionic nature containing R₂Tl⁺ and CN⁻ ions.

We thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for a Research Fellowship (to K.K.B.).

REFERENCES

1. T. N. Srivastava and S. N. Bhattacharya, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **23**, 2445.
2. T. N. Srivastava and S. K. Tandon, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, **36**, 1399.
3. T. N. Srivastava and S. K. Tandon, *Spectrochimica Acta.*, 1971, **27A**, 593.
4. T. N. Srivastava and S. N. Bhattacharya, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 1873.
5. T. N. Srivastava and S. N. Bhattacharya, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 1480.
6. T. N. Srivastava and M. P. Agarwal, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 3416.
7. M. Donadille, M. A. Delmas, J. C. Maire and T. N. Srivastava, *J. Organometal Chem.*, 1968, **15**, 244.
8. T. N. Srivastava and K. K. Bajpai, *J. Organometal Chem.*, 1971, **31**, 1.
9. T. N. Srivastava and K. K. Bajpai, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 1458.
10. T. N. Srivastava, S. K. Tandon and K. K. Bajpai, *Spectrochimica Acta*, 1972, **28A**, 455.
11. D. Seyferth and N. Kahlen, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 809.
12. D. Seyferth and N. Kahlen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 1080.
13. R. A. Cummins and P. Dunn, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1964, **17**, 411.
14. G. E. Coates and R. N. Mukherjee, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 229.
15. H. Zimmer and K. Lubke, *Chem. Ber.*, 1952, **85**, 1119.
16. J. Lorberth, *Chem. Ber.*, 1965, **98**, 1201.
17. F. Challenger and O. V. Richards, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 405.
18. J. G. A. Luitjen and G. J. M. Van der Kerk, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1956, **6**, 49.
19. A. K. Kochetkov and R. K. Freidlina, *Chem. Abs.*, 1950, **44**, 9342.
20. R. G. Gillis and J. L. Occolowitz, *Spectrochimica Acta*, 1963, **19**, 873.
21. L. J. Bellamy, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", John Wiley & Sons, N.Y., 1958.
22. F. A. V. Ebsworth, "Volatile Silicon Compounds", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1963, p. 146.
23. A. Allerhand and P. V. R. Schleyer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 866.
24. E. Sohlemper and D. Britton, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 511.
25. J. S. Thayer and D. P. Strommen, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 383.
26. W. Beck and Schuierer, *Chem. Ber.*, 1964, **97**, 3517.
27. T. A. Bither, W. H. Knoth, R. V. Lindesey (Jr.) and W. H. Sharkey, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4151.
28. H. J. Emelsue and P. R. Evans, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 510.
29. E. A. V. Ebsworth, "Organometallic Compounds of the Group IV Elements", Vol. I, pt. I, Editor A. G. MacDiarmid, Merceel Dekker, Inc. (N.Y.), 1968, p. 42.
30. J. S. Thayer, and R. West, "Advances in Organometallic Chemistry", Vol. V, Ed., F. G. A. Stone and R. West, 1967, p. 169.